

Statistical Analysis Results Using SPSS Software

Baseline Characteristics of Study Participants

a. Normality Test for Age and Baseline Pain Score (NRS0)

Descriptives				
Age	Groups		Statistic	Std. Error
	Tramadol	Mean	43.69	1.956
		95% Confidence Interval for Mean	39.71	
			47.66	
		5% Trimmed Mean	43.56	
		Median	43.00	
		Variance	133.869	
		Std. Deviation	11.570	
		Minimum	21	
		Maximum	69	
		Range	48	
		Interquartile Range	16	
		Skewness	.172	.398
		Kurtosis	-.441	.778
		Metamizole (Antrain)	Mean	40.89
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		36.40	
			45.37	
	5% Trimmed Mean		40.86	
	Median		39.00	
	Variance		170.575	
	Std. Deviation		13.060	
	Minimum		18	
	Maximum		66	
Range	48			
Interquartile Range	22			
Skewness	-.086		.398	
Kurtosis	-.951		.778	
NRS 0	Tramadol		Mean	5.46
		95% Confidence Interval for Mean	5.22	
			5.70	
		5% Trimmed Mean	5.51	
		Median	6.00	

	Variance		.491	
	Std. Deviation		.701	
	Minimum		4	
	Maximum		6	
	Range		2	
	Interquartile Range		1	
	Skewness		-.928	.398
	Kurtosis		-.333	.778
Metamizole (Antrain)	Mean		5.23	.136
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	4.95	
		Upper Bound	5.51	
	5% Trimmed Mean		5.25	
	Median		5.00	
	Variance		.652	
	Std. Deviation		.808	
	Minimum		4	
	Maximum		6	
	Range		2	
	Interquartile Range		1	
	Skewness		-.451	.398
	Kurtosis		-1.310	.778

Tests of Normality

	Groups	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
		Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Age	Tramadol	.082	35	.200*	.985	35	.912
	Metamizole (Antrain)	.104	35	.200*	.962	35	.263
NRS0	Tramadol	.352	35	<,001	.722	35	<,001
	Metamizole (Antrain)	.287	35	<,001	.773	35	<,001

*. This is a lower bound of the true significance.

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

b. Independent Samples t-Test for Age

Independent Samples Test											
		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means							
		F	Sig.	t	df	Significance One-Sided p	Significance Two-Sided p	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
										Lower	Upper
Age	Equal variances assumed	.929	.339	.949	68	.173	.346	2.800	2.949	-3.085	8.685
	Equal variances not assumed			.949	67.026	.173	.346	2.800	2.949	-3.087	8.687

c. Mann–Whitney U Test for Baseline Pain Score (NRS0)

		Ranks		
Groups		N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
NRS0	Tramadol	35	38.13	1334.50
	Metamizole (Antrain)	35	32.87	1150.50
	Overall	70		

Test Statistics^a

	NRS0
Mann-Whitney U	520.500
Wilcoxon W	1150.500
Z	-1.188
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.235

a. Grouping Variable: Group

d. Chi-Square Test for Sex Distribution

Sex * Groups Crosstabulation

Count		Group		Overall
		Tramadol	Metamizole (Antrain)	
Sex	Men	12	7	19
	Women	23	28	51
Overall		35	35	70

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	1.806 ^a	1	.179		
Continuity Correction ^b	1.156	1	.282		
Likelihood Ratio	1.822	1	.177		
Fisher's Exact Test				.282	.141
Linear-by-Linear Association	1.780	1	.182		
N of Valid Cases	70				

a. 0 cells (.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 9,50.

b. Computed only for a 2x2 table

e. Fisher–Freeman–Halton Exact Test for Primary Clinical Diagnosis

Diagnosis * Groups Crosstabulation

Count		Groups		Overall
		Tramadol	Metamizole (Antrain)	
Diagnosis	Tumor/ Ca Mamae	16	12	28
	Tumor Buccal/ Labialis/ Ginggiva/ Maxila	10	12	22
	Tumor Head-neck/ Limfatik (Coli/ Axilla/ Lymphadenitis)	2	8	10
	Tumor Thorax/ Abdomen/ STT/ Gluteus/ Cruris	2	1	3
	Abses/ Infection/ Seroma	4	2	6
	Others (Mixed or Heterogeneous Diagnoses)	1	0	1
	overall		35	35

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)	Point Probability
Pearson Chi-Square	6.353 ^a	5	.273	.270		
Likelihood Ratio	7.016	5	.219	.306		
Fisher-Freeman-Halton Exact Test	6.261			.246		
Linear-by-Linear Association	.033 ^b	1	.855	.928	.464	.071
N of Valid Cases	70					

a. 6 cells (50,0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is ,50.

b. The standardized statistic is -,182.

f. Chi-Square Test and Fisher–Freeman–Halton Exact Test for Procedure Type

Procedure * Groups Crosstabulation

Count

		Groups		
		Tramadol	Metamizole (Antrain)	overall
Prosedure	Biopsy	5	13	18
	Excision	30	22	52
overall		35	35	70

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)	Point Probability
Pearson Chi-Square	4.786 ^a	1	.029	.054	.027	
Continuity Correction ^b	3.665	1	.056			
Likelihood Ratio	4.919	1	.027	.054	.027	
Fisher's Exact Test				.054	.027	
Linear-by-Linear Association	4.718 ^c	1	.030	.054	.027	.021
N of Valid Cases	70					

a. 0 cells (,0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 9,00.

b. Computed only for a 2x2 table

c. The standardized statistic is -2,172.

g. Chi-Square Test and Fisher–Freeman–Halton Exact Test for Procedure Type

Procedure * Groups Crosstabulation

Count

		Groups		
		Tramadol	Metamizole (Antrain)	overall
Prosedure	Biopsy	5	13	18
	Excision	30	22	52
overall		35	35	70

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)	Point Probability
Pearson Chi-Square	4.786 ^a	1	.029	.054	.027	
Continuity Correction ^b	3.665	1	.056			
Likelihood Ratio	4.919	1	.027	.054	.027	
Fisher's Exact Test				.054	.027	
Linear-by-Linear Association	4.718 ^c	1	.030	.054	.027	.021
N of Valid Cases	70					

a. 0 cells (.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 9,00.

b. Computed only for a 2x2 table

c. The standardized statistic is -2,172.

Treatment Effectiveness

a. Normality Test for Change in Pain Score (Δ NRS) by Treatment Group

Report

Groups		NRS0	NRS24	DELta NRS
Tramadol	Mean	5.46	2.26	3.20
	N	35	35	35
	Std. Deviation	.701	.950	.759
Metamizole (Antrain)	Mean	5.23	2.17	3.06
	N	35	35	35
	Std. Deviation	.808	1.098	.684
overall	Mean	5.34	2.21	3.13
	N	70	70	70
	Std. Deviation	.759	1.020	.721

Descriptives

Groups			Statistic	Std. Error	
DELta_NRS	Tramadol	Mean	3.20	.128	
		95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	2.94	
			Upper Bound	3.46	
		5% Trimmed Mean	3.17		
		Median	3.00		
		Variance	.576		
		Std. Deviation	.759		
		Minimum	2		
		Maximum	5		
		Range	3		
		Interquartile Range	1		
		Skewness	.496	.398	

	Kurtosis		.377	.778
Metamizole (Antrain)	Mean		3.06	.116
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	2.82	
		Upper Bound	3.29	
	5% Trimmed Mean		3.06	
	Median		3.00	
	Variance		.467	
	Std. Deviation		.684	
	Minimum		2	
	Maximum		4	
	Range		2	
	Interquartile Range		1	
	Skewness		-.071	.398
	Kurtosis		-.735	.778

Tests of Normality

Groups	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
DElta_NRS Tramadol	.318	35	<,001	.832	35	<,001
Metamizole (Antrain)	.276	35	<,001	.802	35	<,001

Lilliefors Significance Correction

b. Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test for Δ NRS Within the Tramadol and Metamizole Groups

Test Statistics^a

	NRS24 - NRS0
Z	-7.449 ^b
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	<,001

a. Wilcoxon Signed Ranks Test

b. Based on positive ranks.

c. Mann–Whitney U Test for Δ NRS Between Treatment Groups

Test Statistics^a

NRS24 - NRS0	
Z	-7.449 ^b
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	<,001

a. Wilcoxon Signed Ranks Test

b. Based on positive ranks.

d. Adjusted Analysis of Δ NRS Using ANCOVA

Tests of Between-Subjects Effects

Dependent Variable: DELta_NRS1

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Squared	Eta
Corrected Model	.362 ^a	2	.181	.342	.711	.010	
Intercept	516.256	1	516.256	974.880	<,001	.936	
Kelompok	.355	1	.355	.670	.416	.010	
Tindakan	.005	1	.005	.010	.921	.000	
Error	35.480	67	.530				
Total	721.000	70					
Corrected Total	35.843	69					

a. R Squared = .010 (Adjusted R Squared = -.019)

